

PEROXIDASES. PART IV. A METHOD OF ESTIMATING PEROXIDASE ACTIVITY FROM E. M. F. MEASUREMENTS

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It has been shown in a previous paper (Dey, Rengachari and Sitharaman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 390) that potentiometric titrations can be successfully applied for estimating the peroxidase activity of plant saps when hydroquinone is employed as the substrate and the advantages of the method have been referred to therein. Since hydroquinone and its oxidation product, quinone, form a reversible oxidation-reduction system, it was hoped that potential measurements might be employed to find out the unreacted hydroquinone in the peroxidase reaction mixture thus leading to a comparison of the relative merits of the two methods of estimating peroxidase activity.

Haber and Russ (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1904, 47, 257) have shown that the reversible reduction of quinone to hydroquinone could be considered from the electrochemical standpoint and that the Van't Hoff reaction isotherm was applicable, the reaction being similar in character to oxidation and reduction reactions in the case of electrolytes. The reaction taking place is represented by the equation

Their method lay in finding out whether the observed differences in potential of two solutions containing different ratios of hydroquinone-quinone measured separately against a calomel electrode, agreed with the theoretical values calculated from the Van't Hoff expression, keeping the acidity of the solution constant.

These results have been confirmed by Cranger and Nelson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1401), who took into account the actual concentrations of the reactants, the acidity of the solutions which was varied, and the degree of dissociation of quinhydrone, which they always found out when quinone and hydroquinone were present in solution instead of assuming as Haber and Russ (*loc cit.*) had done, that the quinhydrone was completely dissociated.

Stern and Day (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1929, 85, 299) have employed the change in potential that occurs when air is bubbled through a solution of quinhydrone, properly buffered, as a means of detecting certain sufficiently active oxidases or oxygenases, choosing potato oxidase as the most suitable. They have found that the potential rise initially observed under conditions stated above is restored partially by adding further quantities of quinhy-

drone and that the observed potentials compared reasonably with the potentials calculated on the basis of the Van't Hoff equation.

The potential of an inert electrode, *e.g.*, platinum or gold, immersed in a solution containing quinone and hydroquinone is usually given by the expression,

$$\pi = \pi_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{C_Q C_R^2}{C_{HQ}} = \pi_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{C_Q}{C_{HQ}} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln C_R.$$

This oxidation-reduction potential of the quinone-hydroquinone system, involving as it does a feebly ionised or practically unionised organic compound, is dependent on the hydrogen-ion activity of the solution. If, therefore, the reference electrode and the hydrogen-ion concentration of the system be kept constant, the E.M.F. of the system will alter with the ratio of the quinone to hydroquinone. If π be the potential of the quinhydrone electrode, π_1 that of the reference electrode (here 0.1N calomel), then since the quinhydrone electrode is more positive than calomel, the observed E.M.F.

$$E = \pi - \pi_1 = \pi_0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln C_R + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{C_Q}{C_{HQ}} - \pi_1$$

$$= \left[\pi_0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln C_R - \pi_1 \right] + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{C_Q}{C_{HQ}}$$

since π_0 , π_1 and the hydrogen-ion concentrations are kept constant.

$$\therefore E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{C_Q}{C_{HQ}}, \text{ where } E_0 \text{ is the expression within}$$

brackets. If conditions are so chosen that E_0 is constant, then the above expression can be used to compare the E.M.F. of the system as regards observed values for different ratios of quinone to hydroquinone. The expression when $t = 0^\circ$ becomes,

$$E = E_0 + 0.0271 \log \frac{C_Q}{C_{HQ}} = E_0 - 0.0271 \log \frac{C_{HQ}}{C_Q}$$

In the peroxidase reaction the initial condition is represented by the system comprising of (i) the volume of buffer solution added, (ii) volume of sap added, (iii) volume of hydroquinone solution, and (iv) the volume of hydrogen peroxide, the temperature of the reactants and the temperature of the mixture being the same. After a certain interval of time (generally 18 minutes) the reaction is stopped by the addition of hydrochloric acid. The condition then is represented by (i) the volume of the buffer, (ii) the volume of the sap, (iii) the volume of hydroquinone left over, (iv) the volume of hydrogen peroxide left over, (v) the quinhydrone in solution, neglecting

the precipitated amount, and (vi) the volume of hydrochloric acid added for inhibiting the reaction. If the amount of unreacted hydroquinone is to be determined by potential measurements, a study must be made of the variations of the E.M.F. of a solution, with respect to the variations in concentration of hydroquinone, all other conditions enumerated above remaining constant. The concentration of hydroquinone in any other solution which is identical in the matter of every condition can be obtained directly from a hydroquinone concentration—E. M. F. curve. It was this method that was followed in the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Experiments were conducted with the same saps that were employed or the previous investigation (*loc. cit.*) and it was found necessary to submit

FIG. 1.

1-Dip type cal. electrode.
2-Pt foil electrode. 3-Stirrer.
4-Dewar flask.

these saps to longer periods of dialysis (4 to 5 days) to eliminate electrolytes completely. Since temperature is an important factor in potential measurements and the activity of the saps is appreciable at temperatures considerably lower than the room temperature (30° - 32°), it was considered best to carry out these experiments at 0° using a mixture of ice-water and ice in a good silvered wide-mouthed Dewar vessel, the bath being stirred mechanically for avoiding fluctuations of temperature. It was found in trials that the temperature remained constant for periods of 2 to 3 hours. The Dewar vessel was fitted with a bung which carried a Beckmann outer tube, 2" diameter, drawn out to a conical shape at its closed end (*cf.* Fig. 1). This formed the reaction vessel and was closed by a three-holed rubber cork carrying (1) a dip-type calomel electrode (which was designed and made for the purpose since the available dip-type electrodes were of an inconvenient size (*vide* Fig. 1); (2) a platinum foil electrode (Hildebrand type) with an outlet for leading away gas; and (3) a delivery tube for bubbling purified nitrogen gas, partly to keep an inert atmosphere within, since hydroquinone undergoes slow oxidation in air and partly to secure a good stirring of the reaction mixture.

The nitrogen was obtained from a cylinder and was purified by passing through alkaline pyrogallol, concentrated sulphuric acid,

water (conductivity) and finally through fused calcium chloride for drying. Conductivity water was used to prepare all solutions which were preserved in Jena glass bottles. Solutions of hydroquinone (exactly, 3.0%) were freshly prepared before use and preserved in dark amber-coloured bottles. The solutions were delivered from automatic microburettes. For potential measurements, a Leeds and Northrup K-type potentiometer and a portable sensitive mirror galvanometer were used, the voltage readings being accurate to 0.00005 volt. No correction for salt or protein error was applied though quinhydrone was used. The volume was adjusted to a final volume of 20 c.c. of the reaction mixture, which was maintained constant throughout the series of experiments. A buffer of sodium acetate and hydrochloric acid of p_a 4.58 was used. A decinormal calomel electrode (in the dip-type electrode vessel prepared) was used as the reference electrode in view of its temperature coefficient being very low compared with the other calomel

FIG. 2.

electrodes. In all cases sufficient quinhydrone was added to keep the solution saturated with respect to it.

The first stage in the series was to find by trial an indicator or reference solution which will be applicable to all saps, and possessing a constant and reproducible E.M.F. in the absence of hydroquinone. When hydroquinone is added, the E.M.F. gradually diminishes with increase of concentration of the hydroquinone. A reference to Table I (a), (b) will show that when mixtures were made up with 7 c.c. of the buffer (p_n 4.58), 2 c.c. of 2*N* hydrochloric acid, and 11 c.c. of water to make up to the constant volume of 20 c.c., the same initial E.M.F. of 0.2980 volt nearly, was reached. In Table I (c), where hydrogen peroxide (1 c.c. of 1% solution) was added with a corresponding reduction of water, the E.M.F. was unaffected. When increasing quantities of a 3.0% solution of hydroquinone (from 1 c.c. to 5 c.c. were added) the same potentials were registered in all cases (within experimental errors). It took nearly 45 minutes the equilibrium to reach and this interval of time was allowed to elapse in each case before final measurements were taken.

The hydroquinone concentration-E.M.F. relationship of the reference solution is given by the curve in Fig. 2, which was plotted by taking the averages of the three sets of experiments in Table I.

A repetition of the experiments with the three saps separately was made as shown in Tables II, III and IV. 5 C.c. of the sap were added in each case replacing the same volume of water, the total volume of 20 c.c. being maintained. The potentials are found to be in agreement with those in Table I (without the sap under the same conditions). Reference to Tables II (c), III (c) and IV (c) will show that the presence of hydrogen peroxide does not cause any alteration in the potentials, and that the reaction has been completely inhibited by the HCl added. From the measurements it is evident that $E_0 = 0.2980$ volt with $C_Q / C_{H_2O_2} = 1$, i. e., $\log C_Q / C_{H_2O_2} = 0$.

The change of potential with the alteration in the volume of the hydroquinone solution in the experiments with the different saps are plotted in Figures 3, 4 and 5.

The next stage was to study the peroxidase activity as usual with the three saps and estimate the hydroquinone left over by measuring the final potential of the system and comparing with the potentials of the reference solution. 7 C.c. of the buffer (p_n 4.58), 5 c.c. of 3.0% hydroquinone solution and 1 c.c. of 1% hydrogen peroxide were mixed in the reaction vessel cooled to 0°; 5 c.c. of the sap at 0° were added while a current

of nitrogen was bubbling through the solution. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 15 minutes at the end of which exactly 2 c.c. of 2.0*N* hydrochloric acid were quickly added from a microburette, the rate of bubbling of nitrogen being increased to effect a thorough mixing of the reaction mixture so that the reaction might be inhibited quickly. The nitrogen was kept bubbling for 45 minutes continuously at a slower rate at the end of which the E.M.F. was measured. From the E.M.F.—hydroquinone concentration curve of the reference solution, the concentration of the hydroquinone corresponding to the final E.M.F. observed in the test solution was obtained. This represents the hydroquinone (*y*) remaining in

FIG. 3.

solution ; part of the unoxidised hydroquinone combining with the quinone formed to form the quinhydrone which was precipitated on account of its low solubility. Since the amount of hydroquinone taken (*x*) is known (being

equal to 0.15 g. in all cases) and y , the amount of it left in solution is found out by experiment, the amount oxidised is $\frac{x-y}{2}$ corresponding to the quinone part of the quinhydrone formed.

The accuracy was also checked by diluting the reaction mixture to 100 c.c. as usual (*vide* the potentiometric method) and estimating the hydroquinone by potentiometric titration against standard potassium dichromate, the necessary blank experiments to find the intake of the

FIG. 4.

dichromate by the sap being duly performed. The results obtained in both the cases are found to agree well (*vide* Tables V, VI and VII).

The E.M.F. observed was then compared with the E.M.F. calculated theoretically on the following basis from the formula,

$$E = E_0 - 0.0271 \log \frac{C_{H_2Q}}{C_Q}$$

The concentration of the quinone is precisely the concentration obtained by the dissociation of quinhydrone, the solution being saturated with respect to it in all cases, since a precipitation of quinhydrone took place.

This concentration of quinone can be calculated from the solubility of quinhydrone in a solution identical in concentration of the reactants in the reaction mixture at the end of the reaction. 50 C.c. of a solution containing 6.25 c.c. of 3.0% hydroquinone, 17.50 c.c. of buffer (p_H 4.58), 5 c.c. of 2.0N-hydrochloric acid the rest being water was made up, excess of quinhydrone added and the mixture was agitated for two hours at 0° in a bath similar to the one used for the previous experiments. The solution was filtered by suction through cotton wool into another vessel kept in a similar bath at 0°. A definite volume of the solution was pipetted and the total hydroquinone in it determined potentiometrically by titration against standard potassium dichromate. The value for hydroquinone thus obtained is the sum of the hydroquinone initially taken together with the hydroquinone due to the solution of the quinhydrone, the latter being assumed, for the purpose of this investigation to be completely dissociated. By deducting the hydroquinone initially taken, from the total amount of hydroquinone, the hydroquinone part of the quinhydrone dissolved is obtained. The quinone part is equivalent to the hydroquinone thus determined. As a mean of three experiments, the value obtained was 0.03264 g. calculated as quinhydrone in 100 c.c. of the solution; so that in the reaction mixture of 20 c.c., the concentration of quinhydrone is 0.006528 g. which corresponds to 0.003233 g. of quinone and 0.003295 g. of hydroquinone. Now,

$$E = E_0 - 0.0271 \log \frac{C_{H_2Q}}{C_Q}$$

E_0 being 0.2980 volt.

Calculating the potential of the system in Experiment I, Table VII, the amount of hydroquinone left over in solution (from the titration) is 0.0714 g. And since the quinhydrone dissolves to a certain extent and is assumed to have dissociated completely thus increasing the hydroquinone concentration

the amount of hydroquinone (H.Q.) present in solution = $0.0714 + 0.003295$
 = 0.0747 g.

Amount of quinone (Q) in solution = 0.003233 g.

$$E = 0.2980 - 0.0271 \log \frac{0.0747}{0.003233} = 0.2610 \text{ volt (calculated).}$$

$$E = 0.2590 \text{ volt (observed).}$$

The error is, therefore, less than 1%. Similar calculations in all the other cases give similar agreement between the calculated and the observed potentials.

FIG. 5.

Alteration of the E.M.F. with change in Hydroquinone Concentration in the reference Solution.

TABLE I.

Total volume in all cases = 20 c.c. buffer of p_H 4.58 added = 7 c.c. 2*N*-HCl added = 2 c.c.

Vol. of 3.0% H ₂ O ₂ .	(a)		(b)		(c)	
	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	1% H ₂ O ₂ = 1 c.c. Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).
Nil	11 c.c.	0.2980	11 c.c.	0.2982	10 c.c.	0.2980
1 c.c.	10	0.2745	10	0.2740	9	0.2740
2	9	0.2625	9	0.2628	8	0.2630
3	8	0.2545	8	0.2540	7	0.2540
4	7	0.2478	7	0.2473	6	0.2475
5	6	0.2425	6	0.2428	5	0.2427

TABLE II.

Experiments similar to those in Table I, the solutions containing 5 c.c. of dialysed radish (*Raphanus Sativus*) sap. Buffer of p_H 4.58 = 7 c.c. 2*N*-HCl added = 2 c.c.

Vol. of 3.0% H ₂ O ₂ .	(a)		(b)		(c)	
	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	1% H ₂ O ₂ = 1 c.c. Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).
Nil	6 c.c.	0.2990	6 c.c.	0.2980	5 c.c.	0.2985
1 c.c.	5	0.2735	5	0.2745	4	0.2745
2	4	0.2660	4	0.2635	3	0.2635
3	3	0.2555	3	0.2550	2	0.2560
4	2	0.2495	2	0.2490	1	0.2490
5	1	0.2410	1	0.2430	Nil	0.2435

TABLE III.

Experiments similar to those in Table I, the solutions containing 5 c.c. of dialysed chow-chow (*Secchium Edule*) sap. Buffer of p_H 4.58 added = 7 c.c. 2N-HCl taken = 2 c.c.

Vol. of 3.0% H.Q.	(a)		(b)		(c)	
	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	1% H_2CO_3 = 1 c.c. Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).
Nil	6 c.c.	0.2980	6 c.c.	0.2975	5 c.c.	0.2975
1 c.c.	5	0.2755	5	0.2755	4	0.2740
2	4	0.2645	4	0.2647	3	0.2635
3	3	0.2560	3	0.2563	2	0.2550
4	2	0.2483	2	0.2485	1	0.2465
5	1	0.2415	1	0.2420	Nil	0.2415

TABLE IV.

Experiments similar to those in Table I, the solutions containing 5 c.c. of dialysed red radish sap (*Raphanus Sativus*, red variety). Buffer of p_H 4.58 = 7 c.c. 2N-HCl = 2 c.c.

Vol. of 3.0% H.Q.	(a)		(b)		(c)	
	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).	1% H_2CO_3 = 1 c.c. Vol. of water.	E. M. F. (volts).
Nil	6 c.c.	0.2985	6 c.c.	0.2980	5 c.c.	0.2980
1 c.c.	5	0.2735	5	0.2745	4	0.2735
2	4	0.2635	4	0.2640	3	0.2635
3	3	0.2560	3	0.2550	2	0.2555
4	2	0.2485	2	0.2485	1	0.2490
5	1	0.2430	1	0.2430	Nil	0.2430

TABLE V.

Reactions carried out with dialysed radish (*Raphanus Sativus*) sap, as described on p. 282, E.M.F. measured and results checked by titration.

	EXPT. I.	EXPT. II.
E. M. F. measured at the final stage	... 0.2578 ₅ volt.	... 0.2575 volt.
E. M. F. calculated from formula	... 0.2606 volt.	... 0.2608 volt.
H.Q. left in solution (y) obtained from the E. M. F.—H.Q. conc. curve of the ref. soln.	... 0.0745 g.	... 0.0771 g.
∴ Amount of H.Q. oxidised	... 0.0378 g.	... 0.0365 g.
Amount of H.Q. corresp. to $K_2Cr_2O_7$ titration.	... * 0.1119 g.	... † 0.1137 g.
∴ Amount of H.Q. oxidised	... 0.0381 g.	... 0.0363 g.
Amount of H.Q. left as such in solution	... 0.0738 g.	... 0.0774 g.

* Being equivalent to 18.90 c.c. of 0.1076 N- $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

† Being equivalent to 19.20 c.c. of 0.1076 N- $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

TABLE VI.

Reaction carried out with dialysed chow-chow (*Secium Edule*) sap, as described on p. 282, E.M.F. measured and results checked by titrations,

	EXPT. I.	EXPT. II.
E. M. F. measured at the final stage	... 0.2610 volt.	... 0.2615 volt.
E. M. F. calc. from formula	... 0.2622 volt.	... 0.2627 volt.
H.Q. left in solution (y), obtained from the E. M. F.—H.Q. conc. curve of the ref. soln.	... 0.0645 g.	... 0.0624 g.
∴ Amount of H.Q. oxidised	... 0.0428 g.	... 0.0438 g.
Amount of H.Q. corresp. to the $K_2Cr_2O_7$ titration.	... * 0.1072 g.	... † 0.1059 g.
∴ Amount of H.Q. oxidised	... 0.0428 g.	... 0.0441 g.
Amount of H.Q. left as such in soln.	... 0.0644 g.	... 0.0618 g.

* Being equivalent to 18.10 c.c. of 0.1076 N- $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

† Being equivalent to 17.90 c.c. of 0.1076 N- $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

TABLE VII.

Reactions carried out with dialysed red radish (*Raphanus Sativus*, red variety) sap as described on p. 282. E.M.F. measured and results checked by titrations.

	EXPT. I.	EXPT. II.
E. M. F. measured at the final stage	... 0.2590 volt.	... 0.2590 volt.
E. M. F. calc. from formula	... 0.2610 volt.	... 0.2610 volt.
Amount of H.Q. left in soln. (y), obtained from the E. M. F.—H.Q. conc. curve of the ref. soln.	... 0.0708 g.	... 0.0708 g.
∴ Amount of H.Q. oxidised	... 0.0396 g.	... 0.0396 g.
Amount of H.Q. corresp. to the $K_2Cr_2O_7$ titration.	... * 0.1107 g.	... † 0.1107 g.
∴ Amount of H.Q. oxidised	... 0.0393 g.	... 0.0396 g.
Amount of H.Q. left as such in soln.	... 0.0714 g.	... 0.0714 g.

* Being equivalent to 18.70 c.c. of 0.1076 N- $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

† Being equivalent to 18.70 c.c. of 0.1076 N- $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

S U M M A R Y.

Since the hydroquinone and quinone (quinhydrone) form a reversible oxidation-reduction system, for which the Van't Hoff formula has been shown to be applicable, by keeping all factors except the ratio of H_2Q/Q constant, the amount of unreacted hydroquinone (substrate) can be estimated with reasonable accuracy by potential measurements. In this case the hydrogen peroxide left over does not affect the results or introduce any error and therefore need not be destroyed. All that is necessary is to make up a reference solution whose changes in potential have been previously studied for different ratios of hydroquinone to quinone, the concentration of the latter being that obtained by saturation of the solution with respect to quinhydrone. The results obtained show that a greater accuracy is possible with this method.

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